

Introduction

Even though we experience many emotions every day, it is often difficult to find the right words to communicate them. What if we could simply point out emotional expressions to show how we feel?

This idea inspired PrEmo: A pictorial emotion self-report instrument.

The heart of PrEmo is a cartoon character that uses his face, body and voice to express fourteen different emotions. The fourteen cards can be used for measuring emotions and to support people in talking about their feelings.

With the free PrEmo app, you can bring the characters to life. Because the cards do not rely on words, they support cross-cultural research. The characters have been validated in The Netherlands, UK, China, and the USA.

This manual gives you

- instructions for obtaining the application
- definitions of the fourteen PrEmo emotions
- tips and suggestions for using the card set
- colophon with copyright information

PrEmo Emotions

For more information about the emotions, see: www.emotiontypology.com

Pride

The feeling when you possess (or have accomplished) something that exceeds your own expectations, or that others find praiseworthy.

Shame

The feeling when someone knows something bad about you. You believe this to be true, so you also feel bad about yourself.

Admiration

The feeling when you look up to someone who has excellent abilities or impressive accomplishments.

Contempt

The feeling when someone is inferior or unworthy in your eyes; they have done something blameworthy.

Joy

The feeling when something good happens to you. You fulfil a need, achieve something, or make progress towards achieving a goal.

Sadness

The feeling when you have lost something that was important to you, and believe it cannot be undone.

Hope

The feeling when you believe (but are not certain) that something good or desirable may happen in the future.

Fear

The feeling when something can harm you or someone you care about, and you are not sure whether you can do anything about it.

Satisfaction

The feeling when something meets or exceeds your expectations.

Anger

The feeling when someone does something bad that harms or offends you, and you blame that other person.

Desire

The feeling when you anticipate that something will be beneficial once acquired or consumed.

Disgust

The feeling when you find something repulsive and want to avoid having contact with it in any way.

Fascination

The feeling when you encounter something new and interesting that you do not immediately understand.

Boredom

The feeling when there is nothing interesting or engaging to door experience.

PrEmo dynamics

The PrEmo character expresses emotions with movement and sound. You can use the PrEmo application to see the dynamic animations. With the app you can use the camera on your phone to bring the PrEmo cards to life.

Step 1: Install the application

Step 2: Open the app and aim your camera at a PrEmo card. The animation will automatically be projected over the image.

To install the PrEmo app, you can either scan the QR code or use the following link: <https://www.pgyer.com/Ds8J>

Note that you can use the card set with or without the application. The advantage of using the app is that the movement and sound add clarity to the expressions. The disadvantage is that it will take some more time for your respondents to look at all the characters.

Using PrEmo

The emotion cards can be used in interviews, focus groups, or any other conversation in which you want to address or talk about feelings. You can ask your respondent(s) or conversation partner(s) to pick one or more expressions to express their feelings.

You can ask them how they feel about a particular stimulus, such as a product design, an image, a fragrance, an interior, a service encounter, and etcetera. Likewise, you can also ask them what they would like to feel, what they are not feeling, what they felt in previous events, or what they expect to feel in future events.

Examples of questions/tasks you can use in interviews or focus groups:

- Select one or more cards that best express how you feel.
- Place order the cards to express how strong your feelings are.
- Explain in your own words what the card expresses.
- Explain why you feel this way.

The design has been kept simple to support usage versatility. The characters are basically self-explanatory, but if you want you can introduce and discuss them at the start of your conversation. Depending on your conversation needs, you can decide to use the application to include the dynamics, either when introducing the cards, or during the course of the conversation.

Colophon

Production

PrEmo concept and development by Pieter Desmet. Cartoons created by Peter Wassink. Card set production by Yancheng Du in collaboration with Pieter Desmet and Haiian Xue.

Reference

In communication, please refer to this card-set as follows:

Desmet, P.M.A. (2019). PrEmo card set: Male version. Delft, Delft University of Technology. ISBN: 978-94-6384-076-7

Publications

Desmet, P.M.A. (2018). Measuring emotion: Development and application of an instrument to measure emotional responses to products. In: M.A. Blythe & A.F. Monk (Eds.), *Funology 2: from usability to enjoyment* (pp. 391-404). Springer Publishing.

Laurans, G., & Desmet, P.M.A. (2017). Developing 14 animated characters for non-verbal self-report of categorical emotions. *Journal of Design Research*, 15(3/4), 214–233.

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PrEmo

www.premotool.com
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